

Rac-3m

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-164-RAC-10%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	68	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 164 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/3/2022 8:26:56 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/4/2022 4:26:49 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.990	2379083	49.38	240906
2	10.585	2438685	50.62	

Asy-3m (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-164-asy-10%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	4	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 164 asy
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/4/2022 4:10:09 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/4/2022 4:25:03 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.994	165436	5.20	17200
2	10.568	3016111	94.80	212573